

Awareness and Knowledge of e-Commerce through e-Banking Services: Comparing the Perceptions of Saudi Arabian Islamic and Conventional Bank Customers.

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to assess the level of customer awareness of e-commerce through their experience of e-banking services in Saudi Islamic and conventional banks according to the perceptions of the customers, whereby it aims at developing a better understanding of the level of customer awareness of e-commerce based on their opinions and perceptions expressed through a questionnaire survey. The research sample is based on a sample of 198 customers coming from six Saudi banks (out of 12 banks). The findings indicate that the majority of the respondents from both types of banks appear to understand the importance of e-commerce in general and e-banking services in particular. In addition, the findings suggest that customer awareness of e-commerce through their use of e-banking services can play an important role in expanding the use of e-commerce in Saudi Arabia. This is the first paper in the area of customer awareness of e-commerce through e-banking services using a comparative analysis of Islamic and conventional banks in Saudi Arabia, and therefore, the findings and implications of the research offer invaluable information to the industry and policy-makers.

Keywords: customer awareness, e-commerce, e-banking, Islamic and Conventional banks, Saudi Arabia.

1. INTRODUCTION

The extensive use of technology by banks and financial institutions aims to respond to customers' demands by providing efficient, fast and convenient financial services. The extensive use of e-banking services has also expanded into e-commerce areas. With technological development, hence, the way in which we conduct our economic and financial affairs has changed. With the help of globalisation and technology, businesses all over the world are now seen to be taking advantage of expanded e-commerce activities (Kolsaker and Payne, 2002). Similarly, small and medium sized businesses are obtaining rapid growth by using e-commerce as a strategy (Grandón *et al.*, 2011).

This has been the case with the majority of banks including Islamic banks in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region. Thus, the research presented in this paper is part of a larger project on the aspects and uses of e-commerce through e-banking services in both Islamic and conventional banks in Saudi Arabia. The paper explores the bank customers' views on awareness of e-commerce through their use of e-banking services in both types of bank. In doing so, it presents the initial descriptive findings with the objective of developing a clearer understanding of customers' preferences based on their opinions expressed through a questionnaire survey conducted in 2012 in Saudi Arabia. This paper is organised in six sections; Section 2 presents an overview of banking sector, e-commerce and e-banking in Saudi Arabia, while section 3 provides a brief overview of literature review on e-commerce through the use of e-banking to establish a foundation for this study. Section 4 highlights the research methodology and process, whereas section 5 summarises the characteristics of the sample profile. Section 6 presents the findings of inferential analysis on customer awareness of e-commerce through their use of e-banking services. Finally, Section 7 provides a brief discussion and some concluding remarks.

2. AN OVERVIEW OF BANKING SECTOR, E-COMMERCE AND E-BANKING IN SAUDI ARABIA

SAMA is the Central Bank of Saudi Arabia; and is an autonomous body and independent body. In simple terms, SAMA implements the laws and standards for all the banks and provides the necessary regulatory environment. In addition to domestic banks, there are several foreign banks, which operate in Saudi Arabia. This paper, however, only focuses on Saudi Arabian domestic banks, as they have much greater networks of branches than the foreign bank (SAMA Annual Report, 2011). Saudi Arabia has twelve banks and Table 1 shows the details of Saudi Islamic and conventional banks, including information on branches, online-banking, call-centre, ATMs, POS and capital.

Table 1: Details of the Saudi banks within Saudi Arabia

Bank	Branches	Online-Banking	Call-centre	ATM	POS	Capital (SARbn)
Islamic Banks						
Al-Bilad	102	✓	✓	829	925	4
Al-Inma	55	✓	✓	1000	N.A	15
Al-Jazira	66	✓	✓	308	N.A	4
Al-Rajhi	500	✓	✓	3600	2800 0	16.250
Conventional Banks						
Al-Riyad	318	✓	✓	2542	1071 3	30
Arab National	203	✓	✓	1200	1100 0	10
NCB	329	✓	✓	2252	2300 0	20
Samba	68	✓	✓	512	5381	12
Saudi British	80	✓	✓	510	7069	10
Saudi Fransi	83	✓	✓	576	8634	12.05
Saudi Hollandi	44	✓	✓	265	7190	4.76
Saudi Investment	45	✓	✓	324	154	6

Source: www.cdsi.gov.sa/, Bankscope Database (2015) and SAMA annual report (2013).

In fact the link between e-commerce and e-banking services is very clear and important; without e-payment e-commerce would not be possible (Al Saud and Abdallah, 2004). Al-Somali *et al.*, (2009) articulates that Saudi Arabia is a leader in the region for internet banking, recognize that the country should do more to improve customer relations, especially in terms of saving costs. In addition, the adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become one of the key factors in explaining growth discrepancies across the countries in general but particularly in Saudi Arabia; however, there is a need to uplift the general public's awareness about ICT (Al-Maliki, 2013).

According to SAMA (2013) Saudi Arabia ranks at the top in the field of information technology amongst the Arabian states. In addition, Bahaddad *et al.*, (2013) stated that 54% of Saudi companies have websites to present their products. In further providing evidence, Al-Somali *et al.* (2011) conducted research about the Saudi SMEs' adoption of e-commerce, which showed that the level of adoption of e-commerce has not reached to the level of maturity. The results stress that there is a need to improve internet shopping in Saudi SMEs. Furthermore, Elseoud (2014) focused on national economic growth from 2001- 2013 and found that there is a need to increase investment in the infrastructure, to have more users of the internet, and to offer more credit cards to the users in Saudi Arabia. Table 2 shows the growth of internet usage in Saudi Arabia. As can be seen in 2002, only 6% of the population had access to internet, which reached to 66.9% at 2014. This clearly suggests that the public was encouraged to use the facility.

Table 2: Internet Growth in Saudi Arabia, 2002-2014

Year	Internet Users	Population	Penetration Rate
2002	1,400,000	21,494,813	6%
2005	3,000,000	23,329,584	13%
2008	9,300,000	25,787,025	36%
2011	13,600,000	28,376,355	48%
2014	20,070,000	30,000,000	66.9%

Sources: www.cdsi.gov.sa/, www.citc.gov.sa, www.Internet.gov.sa, and www.internetworldstats.com/

3. CONCEPTUAL AND LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several definitions of e-commerce and e-banking: Bidgoli (2002), for example, defines e-commerce as purchasing and selling merchandise and services through the internet. In a similar manner, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2011: 72) defines e-commerce as “the sale or purchase of goods or services, conducted over computer networks by methods specifically designed for the purpose of receiving or placing or orders”. In referring to banking sector, Nitsure (2003: 5377) defines e-banking as the “provision of banking products and services through electronic delivery channels”, which relates e-banking as a specific sub-set of e-commerce. In addition, The Saudi Arabian Monetary Agency (SAMA) defines e-banking as electronic banking services featuring distance services provided by sanctioned banks or their representatives through systems directly controlled by the appropriate bank or otherwise by another body in accordance with the terms of an agreement between the two sides (SAMA, E-banking Rules, 2010).

The emergence of e-commerce can be traced back to 1970s, and since then, e-commerce has developed rapidly involving a number of distinct stages. In its early stages of development, the internet featured a package of communication discipline compiled by Leiner *et al.*, (2009) as part of a programme sponsored by the US Department of Defense. Eventually, the first internet activity emerged in 1973 and was fully developed in 1983.

A number of studies have shown that technological accessibility and awareness of it can change the attitudes of people towards adoption. For example, Al-Majali and Nik (2010) in their research on Jordanian banking found that the technology would be adopted if there were certain attitudes and behaviours that could be accommodated by the customers. All Saudi banks have websites and all of them provide e-banking services to their clients. Moreover, the number of POS in Saudi Arabia in the first quarter of 2013 was 94,894, a significant rise from 72,351 in 2008. In addition, the numbers of ATMs have increased to 13,003 from 8,893 in the same period (SAMA Annual Report, 2013).

In order to protect clients from electronic deception associated with e-banking, and to encourage banks to offer e-banking facilities, SAMA issued the ‘Electronic Banking Rules’. As a precautionary measure the rules regulate e-banking activities, as well as provide advice for banks in relation to risk control with regard to e-banking in order to ensure the protection of clients by raising awareness and protection of privacy and by providing the minimum level of security possible (E-Banking Rules, 2010).

Kalakota and Whinston (1997) argue clearly that the earlier media links could not cut the long distances in between the media and end users. The early 1920s witnessed the emergence of radio, while TV was introduced in 1950s, and was not in line to send the message to the large populations. The video and its links were introduced in 1970s, and computers have become commonly used in 1980s leading to everyday use of internet for recreational, educational but importantly for business purposes.

The facilitation of internet of e-commerce as well as other internet based services has made human life rather easy, while through conducting business in internet individuals have faced risk and security. For instance, Suh and Han (2003) found internet users to be reluctant to share personal information on websites for security reasons during their investigation; they focused on the perceptions of customers regarding e-commerce. The statistical analysis of 502 cases showed that privacy protection had a significant impact in trusting e-commerce.

Chan *et al.*, (2001) argue that web enabling services now help users in banking, stock trading and education as well as in everyday life by providing assistance in finding jobs, travel, insurance *etc.*, while entertainment services are used to watch movies or play electronic games. It is true that customer satisfaction is important when judging the efficiency of any new technology.

Though e-service now appears to be a fairly established concept in the western world, it is still in an emerging condition in the developing countries. For example, Kumbhar (2011) gathered data from the customers of e-banks in India through a survey questionnaire, the results of which indicate that the majority regard e-banking as cost effective, easy to use, and secure. While contact facilities and system efficiency were found to be rather lacking, the overall customers’ perception of e-banking found to be satisfactory.

In highlighting the role of online banking in Samba bank in Saudi Arabia. The results clearly show that bank uses all available external technologies to ensure the satisfaction of their customers. The pivotal role in Samba’s administration in the inter-organisational aspects shows balance, and its purpose is to strengthen the abilities, capabilities, and know-how of e-banking. I should be noted that the Samba group first implemented inter-organisational developments and then added in providing the services to their clients in the country.

Al-Gahtani *et al.*, (2007) study on the cultural differences and the similarities between the North American and Saudi validations of the 'unified theory of acceptance and use of technology' (UTAUT). They found that IT in the organisational perspectives entirely affected the both societies in terms of cultural differences. Sohail and Sheikh (2008) conducted research in Saudi Arabia, for which the data were obtained from banks, to investigate how they provided online banking along with the role of services. Their results show that four factors have an impact, to varying degrees, on customers' use of e-banking: efficiency, security, fulfilment and responsiveness.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION

The data for this study was collected from a questionnaire schedule, which was distributed to customers of both Islamic and conventional banks in Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire was designed according to the research question in association with the literature on e-commerce and e-banking services.

In order to improve the consistency and effectiveness of the findings, it was decided that a relatively large sample size of bank customers would be considered. For the purpose of time-saving and efficiency, a detailed questionnaire was designed and distributed with the objective of gathering primary data to identify respondents' understandings, perceptions and knowledge on the subject matter.

After careful consideration, six main statements in relation to customer awareness of e-commerce and their use of e-banking services, based on the Likert scale (1-5), were included in the questionnaire along demographic and other related questions. The six main statements were:

- (i) It provides me with more options and benefits;
- (ii) Helps in everyday purchases;
- (iii) E-commerce is compatible with modern lifestyle;
- (iv) Gives great benefits to customers leading to increased customer loyalty;
- (v) Has created social communities between internet merchants; and
- (vi) Easy to use.

The survey questionnaire was administered during May to July 2012 in the Saudi Arabian cities of Riyadh, Alkarj, Jeddah, Makkah, Taif, Dammam, and Alkubr. Instead of focusing on the respondents in the banks' branches, the researcher used a different approach as it is believed that the customers who were using e-banking services would not normally visit the branch. Thus, with a purposive sampling, e-banking service users were located and the questionnaire was given to them to complete. Through such an exercise, 250 questionnaires were distributed (125 each in Islamic and conventional banks). It should be noted that the whole process of questionnaire administration took nearly three months.

The researcher was available in Saudi Arabia to answer any possible questions raised by the respondents. By the end of August 2012, all 250 questionnaires had been returned; however 52 of them were excluded as they were not fully completed. This means 198 questionnaires were used for data analysis. Table 3 illustrates the questionnaire response rate for both Islamic and conventional banks.

Table 3: Questionnaire Response Rate

Type of Bank	Distributed	Received	% Completion
Islamic	125	104	83.2%
Conventional	125	94	75.2%
Total	250	198	79.0%

The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis through SPSS software version 20. The calculations were made for descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, frequencies, and ranking of various questions; and also non-parametric tests were utilized to test the significance of mean differences, if any existed.

After the collection of primary data via the questionnaire, Cronbach's Alpha Test, as a regularly used measure in statistics, was used to measure the internal consistency reliability, for which at least 0.70 is accepted as the basis of reliability (Cronbach, 1951) to judge the consistency of the variables and how these variables attribute (Fujun *et al.*,

2007). As can be seen in Table 4, Cronbach's alpha values were established at 0.906 and 0.874 for Islamic and conventional banks respectively, which indicates that the base of testing the attributes to be reliable and preferable.

Table 4: Reliability Statistics (Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient) for Islamic and Conventional Banks

Factor	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	
		Islamic Banks	Conventional Banks
Knowledge about e-commerce	6	0.906	0.874

Finally, it should be noted that the issues relating to informed consent and confidentiality of the information within the framework of academic ethics were followed throughout the survey.

5. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SAMPLE PROFILE

This section provides a summary of the sample profile investigated, based on type of bank, frequency, sub-total of cumulative total, and cumulative total for the Islamic banks (Alinma, Al-Jazira and Al-Rajhi) and the conventional banks (Arab National, Saudi Fransi and Samba). Table 5 depicts that the total number of respondents was 198, with 52.5% of the respondents representing Islamic banks and 47.4% representing conventional banks.

Table 5: Profile of the Participants

Islamic Banks	Frequency	% of Sub-Total	% of Total
Alinma	34	32.7	17.1
Al-Jazira	30	28.8	15.1
Al-Rajhi	40	38.5	20.2
Sub-Total	104	100.0	52.5
Conventional Banks			
Arab National	32	34.0	16.1
Saudi Fransi	30	31.9	15.2
Samba	32	34.0	16.1
Sub-Total	94	100.0	47.4
Total	198		100.0

Note: totals may not add to 100.0% due to rounding effect.

The characteristics of the respondents in relation to their gender, nationality, age category, monthly income, highest educational qualifications, occupation and region are presented in Table 6, which also provides the variation in the groups and the category of the respondents. The percentages for each characteristic are shown separately.

As can be seen in Table 6, 56.1% of the participants in the research were males, while 43.9% were female. Considering the gender segregation in Saudi Arabia, this study should be considered successful in attracting a female sample of almost 44%. With regards to the nationality of the respondents, 67.7% of respondents were Saudi nationals and 32.3% non-Saudis. As for age distribution of the sample, the results in Table 6 shows that 70.7% of the sample population were aged 45 or below. More specifically, the largest percentage, 33.3%, were in the 26-35 year old category, a further 26.8% were in the 36-45 age group, and just 16.2% in the 46-55 years age group.

Table 6: Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable Group	Frequency (Valid)	% (Valid)	Mean	Standard Deviation
Gender				
Male	111	56.1	1.44	0.498
Female	87	43.9		
Nationality				
Saudi	134	67.7		
Sudanese	9	4.5		
Indian	9	4.5	2.18	1.942
Pakistani	10	5.1		
Egyptian	13	6.6		
Yemeni	14	7.1		
Syrian	9	4.5		
Age category				
18 - 25 years	21	10.6		
26 - 35 years	66	33.3	2.88	1.199
36 - 45 years	53	26.8		
46 - 55 years	32	16.2		
Over 55 years	26	13.1		
Monthly income				
Less than 4001 SR	44	22.2		
4001 - 8000 SR	46	23.2		
8001 - 12000 SR	34	17.2	2.90	1.491
12001 - 16000 SR	46	23.2		
16001 - 20000 SR	16	8.1		
More than 20000 SR	12	6.1		
Highest educational qualifications				
Below High School	40	20.2		
High School	56	28.3	2.42	0.935
Bachelor degree	80	40.4		
Master degree or above	22	11.1		
Occupation				
Student	18	9.1		
Private sector employee	63	31.8		
Public sector employee	90	45.5	2.78	1.144
Private business	7	3.5		
Retired	11	5.6		
unemployed	9	4.5		
Region				
Riyadh Region	65	32.8		
Western Region	95	48.0	1.86	0.710
Eastern Region	38	19.2		

The 18-25 years old category made up 10.6% and those over 55 years of age constituted only 13.1%, with the mean value for the age category being 2.88. This implies that the majority of respondents were young people, who are employed or run their own businesses. The results for monthly income, highest educational qualifications and occupation are also shown in Table 6. In terms of monthly income, 62.6% of respondents earned within the range of SAR4,001 to SAR12,000, followed by those earning in the range of SAR12,001 to SAR16,000, which constitute 23.2% of the sample. The mean value calculated was 2.90 implying that the average income in the sample was somewhere between the two ranges of SAR4000-SAR12000 and SAR12001-SAR16000. As regards to educational qualifications, 51.5% of respondents declared that they had bachelor or master's degrees or above compared to 48.5% respondents who had high school education or lower level. The mean value calculated was 2.42.

Concerning occupation, 45.5% of the sample came from public sector employment, with 31.8% from the private sector; 9.1% were students, followed by 5.6% retired and 3.5% being in private business, while the unemployed represented 4.5%. The mean value was 2.78, which means that the typical respondent was either a private or public

employee. The final category in the study was region. Almost one-half of the respondents, 48.0%, were from the Western region, followed by Riyadh with 32.8% and Eastern Region, with only 19.2%, and the mean value was 0.710.

In summary, it can be said that the majority of the respondents in each demographic were Saudi males, aged between 26-35, earning range being somewhere between SAR4,001-SAR8,000 and SAR12,001-SAR16,000 categories, with bachelor degrees as their highest educational qualifications, employed in the public sector and predominantly from the Western region.

6. EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

This section presents the initial descriptive statistical findings regarding the customer awareness of e-commerce through their use of e-banking services in Saudi banks, which includes analysing the responses given to a number of statements. The results can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: Mean Ranking of Customers’ Knowledge of E-Commerce and E-Banking Services

Knowledge about E-Commerce	Islamic Banks		Conventional Banks	
	Mean	Ranking	Mean	Ranking
Provides me with more options and benefits such as save time and money	3.7596	1	3.5957	2
Helps in everyday purchases	3.2788	6	3.3298	5
Is compatible with modern lifestyle	3.4423	3	3.4574	3
Leads to increase customer loyalty	3.3654	5	3.2553	6
Has created social communities between Internet merchants	3.4135	4	3.3830	4
Provides easy use	3.7212	2	3.7128	1

Table 7 summarises the results for the knowledge of e-commerce and e-banking services for the customers of Islamic and conventional banks. As can be seen from the ranking of mean values, the customers of both types of banks have chosen the same preference order for two of the six statements.

The research focuses on the development of inferential statistical analysis based on the statistical significance of control variables in the answers provided by the participants of the survey. These control variables are based on the demographic categories: ‘gender’, ‘nationality’, ‘age category’, ‘monthly income’, ‘highest educational qualifications’, ‘occupation’ and ‘region’.

In searching for the factors determining respondents’ knowledge of e-commerce and e-banking services for Islamic and conventional banks, non-parametric analysis was utilised whereby mean difference analysis is conducted. In other words, the inferential statistical results are based on testing the mean differences between participants’ preferences for the given statements in relation to each control variable by use of Independent Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test (K-W Test) and the Mann-Whitney U Test (M-WU Test).

The K-W Test and M-WU test for the control variables with the group categories of customer’s knowledge of e-commerce and e-services for Islamic and conventional banks are presented in Table 8 to Table 14. It should be noted that this papers only reports the significant results.

Table 8 shows level of significance for the control variables for the statement that ‘e-commerce provides me with more options and benefits’ for both bank types. As can be seen, four control variables were found to be significant for this statement: age category, monthly income, highest educational qualifications and occupation. The highest mean ranking is sub-groups are identified as the most important determining factor. In the case of Islamic banks, the ‘age’ category control variable is statistically significant with *p*-value of 0.000, and the highest mean rank was that for ‘36-45 years-old’ with a value of 66.91. The lowest mean rank was for the subgroup of ‘over 55 years-old’ with a value of 15.44. In contrast, ‘monthly income’, as a control variable, is not significant with *p*-value of 0.061.

Table 8: Significance of Control Variables on the Statement ‘E-commerce provides me with more options and benefits’ such as save time and money

Group (Control Variables)	Group Categories	Islamic Banks		Conventional Banks		Test
		Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	
Age category	18 - 25 years	59.30	0.000	42.86	0.003	KW Test
	26 - 35 years	59.53		53.85		
	36 - 45 years	66.91		56.62		
	46 - 55 years	45.63		38.41		
	Over 55 years	15.43		23.71		
		4		5		
Monthly income	Less than SAR4001	41.22	0.061	35.08	0.020	KW Test
	SAR4001 - 8000	44.71		42.17		
	SAR8001 - 12000	62.91		52.76		
	SAR12001 - 16000	61.06		55.05		
	SAR16001 - 20000	59.31		54.33		
	More than SAR20000	45.44		76.13		
Highest educational qualifications	Below High School	23.68	0.000	24.50	0.000	KW Test
	High School	54.72		48.77		
	Bachelor degree	59.34		53.39		
	Master’s degree or above	72.14		68.25		
		4		5		
Occupation	Student	59.30	0.001	31.81	0.048	KW Test
	Private sector employee	52.33		44.79		
	Public sector employee	59.31		56.59		
	Private business	57.51		35.17		
	Retired	11.31		31.33		
	Unemployed	37.93		28.50		

Furthermore, the table clearly shows that the ‘highest educational qualifications’ as control variable is significant at 5% critical level, where the ‘Master’s degree or above’ category scored the highest mean rank with a value of 72.14, while the lowest mean rank was for the ‘below high school’ category and its accompanying a value of 23.68 with a *p*-value of 0.000. The final control variable significant in this statement is ‘occupation’. Those respondents coming from a ‘public sector employee’ achieved the highest mean rank with a value of 59.31, whereas the lowest mean rank was recorded for the ‘retired category with a rank of 11.31. The *p*-value for the variable was 0.001, which underlines difference in the participants to this statement.

For conventional banks, age category is significant as a control variable for the statement that ‘e-commerce provides me with more options and benefits’ at 5% with *p*-value of 0.003. The category of ‘36-45 years-old’ achieved the highest mean rank at 56.62, and the lowest mean rank was given to category of ‘over 55 years-old’ with a value of 23.75. It can be seen that monthly income is significant at 5% and this is clarified by the estimated *p*-value of 0.020. Furthermore, for the control variable of ‘more than SAR20,000’ secured the highest mean rank with a value of 76.14 while the lowest mean rank went to the ‘less than SAR4001’ subgroup with a value of 35.08. The control variable of ‘educational qualifications’ is significant 5% with *p*-value of 0.000. ‘Master’s degree or above’ group achieved the highest mean rank with 68.25 and ‘below high school’ category recorded the lowest mean rank with a value of 24.50. The last control variable in this statement ‘occupation’ is also significant at 5%. The *p*-value for occupation is 0.048. The highest value achieved in this control variable was value of 56.59 by the ‘public sector employee’ subgroup, while the ‘unemployed’ subgroup had the lowest mean rank with a value of 28.50.

It should be recognised that the significant control variables in this statement were recorded as the highest mean ranks for the same subcategories in three of four control variables but in varying values.

Table 9 shifts the focus to the statement that ‘e-commerce helps in everyday purchases’ through three significant control variables: age, education attainment and occupation.

Table 9: Significance of Control Variables on the Statement ‘e-commerce helps in everyday purchases’

Group (Control Variables)	Group Categories	Islamic Banks		Conventional Banks		Test
		Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	
Age category	18 - 25 years	58.70	0.000	55.05	0.004	KW Test
	26 - 35 years	60.61		57.03		
	36 - 45 years	66.15		47.27		
	46 - 55 years	40.91		39.81		
	Over 55 years	19.44		22.55		
Highest educational qualifications	Below High School	30.25	0.000	26.58	0.000	KW Test
	High School	63.09		47.42		
	Bachelor degree	53.48		53.90		
	Master’s degree or above	66.93		66.88		
Occupation	Student	75.65	0.000	47.94	0.140	KW Test
	Private sector employee	42.27		42.05		
	Public sector employee	61.29		54.73		
	Private business	32.63		20.00		
	Retired	23.31		0		
	Unemployed	35.14		55.50		
				40.25		

As can be seen, among the Islamic banks the ‘age’ category control variable is significant at 5% with *p*-value of 0.000, the highest mean rank is for 36-45 year-olds with a value of 66.15, whilst the lowest mean rank was for the subgroup of over 55 year-olds with a value of 19.44. In addition, the control variable of ‘highest educational qualifications’ is

significant at 5%, with the *p*-value of 0.000. The subgroup for ‘Master’s degree or above’ scored the highest mean rank with 66.93, whereas the lowest mean rank was for ‘below high school’ category at 30.25. The last significant control variable for Islamic banks in relation to ‘helps in everyday purchases’ is ‘occupation’. The occupation control variable is significant at 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.000. The highest mean rank achieved by subgroup for those of ‘student’ with the value of 75.65. In contrast, the lowest mean rank was scored for the subgroup of ‘retired’ at 23.31. For conventional banks, age category is found to be significant control variable on the suggestion that ‘e-commerce provides me with more options and benefits’ at 5% with *p*-value of 0.004. The category of ‘26-35 years-old’ achieved the highest mean rank at 57.03, and the lowest mean rank was given to category of ‘over 55 years-old’ with a value of 22.55. In addition, the ‘highest educational qualifications’ control variable was significant at the level of 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.000. The ‘Master’s degree or above’ category scored the highest mean rank at 66.88 and ‘below high school’ subgroup achieved the lowest mean rank with a value of 26.58. In contrast, the ‘occupation’ control variable is not significant at level of 5% with a *p*-value of 0.140.

Table 10: Significance of Control Variables on the Statement ‘e-commerce is compatible with modern lifestyle’

Group (Control Variables)	Group Categories	Islamic Banks		Conventional Banks		Test
		Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	
Age category	18 - 25 years	78.55	0.000	42.55	0.035	KW Test
	26 - 35 years	59.66		58.29		
	36 - 45 years	55.96		46.54		
	46 - 55 years	45.84		41.56		
	Over 55 years	21.38		31.50		
Highest educational qualifications	Below High School	31.52	0.001	34.83	0.039	KW Test
	High School	58.67		46.02		
	Bachelor degree	55.87		51.69		
	Master’s degree or above	64.50		63.81		
Occupation	Student	71.70	0.001	44.19	0.654	KW Test
	Private sector employee	51.38		44.36		
	Public sector employee	55.29		52.86		
	Private business	70.79		40.86		
	Retired	5		3		
	Unemployed	14.94		44.67		
		41.07		31.75		

Table 10 presents the findings for the statement that ‘e-commerce is compatible with modern lifestyle’. In this statement three control variables are shown: age category, highest educational qualifications, and occupation. As can be seen, for Islamic banks, the ‘age’ category is significant 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.000, indicating differences between participants for the current statement. The subgroup of ‘18-25 years-old’ scored the highest mean rank with a value of 78.55, whereas the lowest mean rank went to the ‘over 55 years-old’ group. In addition, the control variable of ‘highest educational qualifications’ is significant at the level of 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.001. This control variable was divided into different academic degrees: ‘Master’s degree or above’ category achieved a high value at 64.50, while ‘below high school’ subgroup attained the lowest mean rank with a value of 31.52. Finally, the ‘occupation’

control variable was significant at the level of 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.001. Among the subgroups, ‘student’ achieved the highest value at 71.70, and the lowest mean rank was awarded to ‘retired’ with 14.94.

With regards to conventional banks, the control variable of ‘age’ is significant at 5%, with *p*-value at 0.035, the group of ‘26-35 years-old’ scored the highest mean with a value of 58.29, whilst ‘over 55 years-old’ category registered the lowest value at 31.50. In addition, the ‘highest educational qualifications’ control variable was significant at the level of 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.039. The ‘Master’s degree or above’ category obtained the highest mean rank at 63.81 and ‘below high school’ subgroup achieved the lowest mean rank with a value of 34.83. In contrast, the ‘occupation’ control variable is not significant at level of 5% with a *p*-value of 0.654.

Table 11: Significance of Control Variables on the Statement ‘e-commerce gives great benefits to customers lead to increased customer loyalty’

Group (Control Variables)	Group Categories	Islamic Banks		Conventional Banks		Test
		Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	
Age category	18 - 25 years	47.90	0.000	38.68	0.051	KW Test
	26 - 35 years	63.04		55.56		
	36 - 45 years	61.80		51.75		
	46 - 55 years	47.44		40.22		
	Over 55 years	21.69		32.80		
Highest educational qualifications	Below High School	29.09	0.000	33.44	0.058	KW Test
	High School	53.54		47.76		
	Bachelor degree	55.92		52.44		
	Master’s degree or above	76.57		56.44		
Occupation	Student	65.30	0.006	46.25	0.961	KW Test
	Private sector employee	59.21		45.73		
	Public sector employee	52.91		50.01		
	Private business	1		46.67		
	Retired	61.75		7		
	Unemployed	16.25		50.00		
	44.36	35.50				

Table 11 highlights the significance of control variables, ‘age’, ‘highest education qualification’ and ‘occupation, on the statement that ‘e-commerce gives great benefits to customers lead to increased customer loyalty’.

For Islamic banks, the ‘age’ category control variable is statistically significant at the level of 5%, with an accompanying *p*-value of 0.000. The ‘26-35 years-old’ group achieved a high mean rank of 63.04, while ‘over 55 years-old’ division received 21.69, which was the lowest mean. The ‘highest educational qualifications’ variable, is also significant at 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.000. The ‘Master’s degree or above’ group has the highest mean rank at 76.57, while ‘below high school’ subgroup scored the lowest mean at 29.09. In addition, the ‘occupation’ control

variable is significant at level of 5% with a *p*-value of 0.006. The ‘student’ subgroup achieved the highest value at 65.30, whereas the lowest mean rank was given to ‘retired’ group with 16.25.

In connection with conventional banks, none of the control variables in relation to this statement were found to be significant at the 5% critical level. The *p*-values of control variables of ‘age’, ‘highest educational qualifications’ and ‘occupation’ are 0.051, 0.058 and 0.961 respectively.

Table 12: Significance of Control Variables on the Statement ‘e-commerce has created social communities between internet merchants’

Group (Control Variables)	Group Categories	Islamic Banks		Conventional Banks		Test
		Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	
Age category	18 - 25 years	52.00	0.000	61.27	0.347	KW Test
	26 - 35 years	62.24		48.19		
	36 - 45 years	64.11		46.58		
	46 - 55 years	36.16		41.56		
	Over 55 years	28.25		42.10		
Highest educational qualifications	Below High School	40.27	0.027	33.47	0.087	KW Test
	High School	56.98		51.12		
	Bachelor degree	51.18		50.67		
	Master’s degree or above	68.61		50.25		

Table 12 shows the significance of the differences of opinions of the respondents in relation to the statement that ‘e-commerce has created social communities between internet merchants’, through two categories: ‘age’ and ‘highest educational qualifications’.

In Islamic banks, the ‘age’ control variable is statistically significant at the level of 5%, with a *p*-value of 0.000, while the ‘36-45 years-old’ subgroup scored the highest mean rank with a value of 64.11, while the lowest value went to the ‘over 55 years-old’ group with a value of 28.25. In addition, the ‘highest educational qualifications’ category is significant at the level of 5% with a *p*-value of 0.027. The ‘Master’s degree or above’ category achieved the highest mean ranking at 68.61, while the subgroup ‘below high school’ scored the lowest mean rank with a value of 40.27.

As for the conventional banks, none of the control variables we statistically significant, as the two control variables produced *p*-values with 0.347 and 0.087 respectively.

Table 13: Significance of Control Variables on the Statement ‘e-commerce provides easy use’

Group (Control Variables)	Group Categories	Islamic Banks		Conventional Banks		Test
		Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	Mean Rank	Asym p. Sig. (p)	
Age category	18 - 25 years 26 - 35 years 36 - 45 years 46 - 55 years Over 55 years	64.90 58.63 61.11 47.91 21.41	0.000	54.73 57.52 47.65 37.97 23.35	0.003	KW Test
Monthly income	Less than 4001 SR 4001 - 8000 SR 8001 - 12000 SR 12001 - 16000 SR 16001 - 20000 SR More than 20000 SR	46.58 45.24 54.15 57.38 54.69 64.75	0.493	37.47 41.47 58.15 56.14 64.17 33.63	0.037	KW Test
Highest educational qualifications	Below High School High School Bachelor degree Master degree or above	26.95 57.35 56.50 71.82	0.000	17.89 53.02 51.89 72.19	0.000	KW Test
Occupation	Student Private sector employee Public sector employee Private business Retired Unemployed	64.15 53.04 56.44 52.00 19.00 43.86	0.015	41.19 44.65 55.41 26.50 39.33 17.75	0.100	KW Test
Region	Riyadh Region Western Region Eastern Region	54.88 51.21 51.11	0.822	59.66 42.07 42.98	0.014	KW Test

Table 13 exhibits the significance of control variables on the statement that 'provides easy use'. For Islamic banks, the 'age' control variable is found to be significant with 5%, as the p -value is 0.493. The '18-25 years-old' subgroup is the highest value at 64.90, while the lowest mean rank is for 'over 55 years-old' with a value of 21.41. The 'highest educational qualifications' control variable is also statistically significant at level of 5% with a p -value at 0.000. The 'Master's degree or above' category recorded the highest mean rank at 71.82 and the lowest mean was the 'below high school' grouping with a value of 26.95. In addition, occupation control variable was found to be statistically significant at 5% with a p -value of 0.015. The 'student' group achieved the highest mean rank of 64.15, while the 'retired' group recorded the lowest value at 19.00. In contrast, the 'monthly income' control variable and the 'region' control variable were found to be not statistically significant at 5% with p -values of 0.493 and 0.822 respectively.

As can be seen in Table 14, in the case of conventional banks, the 'age' control variable is statistically significant with a p -value of 0.003. The highest mean rank was for the '26-35 years-old' group with a value of 57.52 and the lowest mean was obtained by 'over 55 years-old' category with a value of 23.35. The 'monthly income' control variable is also statistically significant with a p -value of 0.037. The 'SAR16001-20000' subgroup had the highest mean rank at 54.69, while 'more than SAR20000' group was the lowest mean with a value of 33.63. Thus, the results identify a clear distinction between the answers of the participants.

In addition, the 'highest educational qualifications' control variable is significant at level of 5% with a p -value of 0.000. The highest mean rank went to the 'Master's degree or above' category with a value of 72.19 and the lowest value was for the 'below high school' subgroup at 17.89. The 'region' control variable was also statistically significant at 5%, with a p -value at 0.014. The highest mean was for 'Riyadh region' at 59.66, whereas the lowest mean was recorded by the group for 'Western region' with a value of 42.07. In contrast, the 'occupation' control variable is not significant at the level of 5% with a p -value of 0.100.

In summary, the findings from the application of K-W and M-WU tests are summarised in Table 14, which shows that the control variables of 'gender' and 'nationality' are not significant for any of the statements of customer awareness of e-commerce and e-banking services in Islamic and conventional Saudi banks in this study. Whilst the findings suggest that the majority of Islamic banks customers in the age group 18-45 tend to be more aware of e-commerce, while for the conventional banks customers, the age group 26-35 appear to be significant.

Table 14: The Highest Significant Subcategories among the Control Variables on Respondents' Knowledge of E-Commerce and E-Banking Services

Statement	Age category		Monthly income		Educational		Occupation		Region	
	Islamic	Conventional	Islamic	Conventional	Islamic	Conventional	Islamic	Conventional	Islamic	Conventional
1) E-commerce provides me with more options and benefits	36-45 years	36-45 years	None	More than SAR20000	Master's degree or above	Master's degree or above	Public sector employee	Public sector employee	None	None
2) E-commerce helps in everyday purchases	36-45 years	26-35 years	None	None	Master's degree or above	Master's degree or above	Student	None	None	None
3) E-commerce is compatible with modern lifestyle	18-25 years	26-35 years	None	None	Master's degree or above	Master's degree or above	Student	None	None	None
4) E-commerce gives great benefits to customers lead to increased customer loyalty	26-35 years	None	None	None	Master's degree or above	None	Student	None	None	None
5) E-commerce has created social communities between internet merchants	36-45 years	None	None	None	Master's degree or above	High School	None	None	None	None
6) E-commerce provides easy use	18-25 years	26-35 years	None	16001-20000 SR	Master's degree or above	Master's degree or above	Student	None	None	Riyadh Region

As final summary of result for Table 14, the findings suggest that 'monthly income' category is not significant for any statements of customer awareness in e-commerce through e-banking in the Islamic banks and in majority of cases for the conventional banks. Furthermore, in relation to 'educational qualifications', in all cases in Islamic banks and in four cases in conventional banks, customers with 'Master's degree and above' is statistically significant. This may imply that educated individuals tend to attach much greater weight to an awareness of e-commerce and e-banking, which is also echoed in the 'occupation' category; in most cases the majority of Islamic bank customers were identified as students who have sufficient knowledge of the technology available. Conversely, no occupation group was identified as statistically significant in conventional banks. In relation to the 'regional' category, it is not possible to reach any conclusive result as two which region has the better awareness and knowledge on e-banking.

In providing an overview for Table 14, it can be stated that the Islamic bank customer awareness of e-commerce and e-banking in Saudi Arabian banking is much more positive than those of the conventional banks.

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper aimed at collating and analysing the views of the sampled participants about their awareness of e-commerce and e-banking services in Islamic and conventional Saudi banks. As the results of the data collected through questionnaire analysis show that the customers of both types of banks choose the same preference order for two of the six statements. Although in the remaining cases there are differences in ranking orders, there is very little differences in the mean values. Moreover, the findings of the inferential statistical analysis to determine the significance of the differences in the opinions expressed in relation to the six statements were presented through a number of control variables analysed by the use of non-parametric tests.

The analysis of the views of the respondents concerning their knowledge of dealing, using and practicing e-commerce indicates that neither 'gender' nor 'nationality' are statistically significant variables for any of the statements in either banking types. For the 'age' category control variable, it is interesting to note that in majority of cases, the respondents in the '18-25' and '36-45 years-old' subgroups are found to be the most frequent users for Islamic banks, thus indicating their familiarity with, and knowledge of, both the questions proposed in the initial survey. In contrast, in the 'age' category control variable for conventional banks the '26-35 years-old' subgroup has the highest mean. In addition, while the 'monthly income' control variable is found not to be statistically significant for the majority of participants in the Islamic and conventional banks, despite a few cases where some subgroups have appeared to be significant, there is no clear cut conclusion for the conventional banks customers.

With regard to the 'highest educational qualifications' control variable, only the 'Master's degree or above' category is found to be significant for Islamic banks and conventional banks. The most significant control variable in relation to the six statements appears to be that of the 'occupation', given that it involves participants from different positions who have knowledge about the e-banking services. The subgroup of 'student' has the highest mean for the participants from Islamic banks, but it is not significant for the participants from the conventional banks. Similarly, the 'region' control variable proved to be neutral as non of the region is found to be statistically significant, with the exception of 'Riyadh region' which is found to be significant in the case of conventional banks.

In consideration of the respondents' views about their knowledge of e-commerce and e-services, it can be concluded that the customers of Islamic and conventional banks tend to perform similarly. Thus, it is fair to argue that there are a number of similarities that were found between Islamic and conventional banks based on customer knowledge. In both banks, the research found that gender, nationality and regions are statistically insignificant determinants of the mean difference for the six variables identified at the beginning of the study, whilst age, qualifications and occupation were found to be statistically significant in most cases.

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